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**Efficacy of National Learning Camp to
Literacy and Numeracy of Grade 7 Learners**
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Abstract:

Literacy and numeracy skills are very important competencies that are general and basic skills in education. In the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), Filipino learners performed below average thus indicating a gap in the Philippine Educational System in literacy and numeracy. To address the gap, the Department of Education proposed the implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) in 2023. This study aimed to determine the efficacy of the NLC in the learners' literacy and numeracy performance. The study conducted a single-group analysis, which showed a highly significant difference in the pretest and posttest results of the respondents in both literacy and numeracy. These findings highlight the efficacy of the NLC in improving literacy and numeracy performance. The study's results provide valuable contributions to teaching, offering an alternative setting to enrich learning experiences and improve important competencies such as literacy and numeracy.

Keywords: Alternative Learning Experience, Literacy, National Learning Camp, Numeracy, Summer Class

Introduction:

Education is the cornerstone of a nation's progress and development, and ensuring that students acquire essential literacy and numeracy skills is fundamental to this process. Literacy and numeracy skills are very important competencies that are general and basic skills in education. According to study, early proficiency in reading and numeracy determines student achievement in higher education. In simple terms, literacy abilities are not just reading proficiency, but also the capacity to use these abilities to clarify, connect, and evaluate, comprehend ideas in a context, and distinctly discern the intricacies of the globe and how they are used in daily life. On the other hand, numeracy skills can be interpreted as the ability to apply mathematical concepts in life and the ability to interpret quantitative information that is around us. According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), numeracy skills are a person's ability to implement, formulate, analyze, and interpret mathematics in various contexts. Numeracy skills are not only understanding theoretically, but also a person's ability to use knowledge and skills that are closely related to mathematical modeling, interpreting, and evaluating results.

The Philippines participated in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) for the first time in 2018. The results showed that 15-year-old students in the Philippines scored lower in reading and mathematics than those in most other participating countries and economies. In reading comprehension, the Philippines scored 340 points, compared to OECD average of 487. This means that the average Filipino student in PISA 2018 performed two levels below the average of OECD student. In mathematics, the Philippines scored 353 points, compared to an OECD average of 489. This means that the average Filipino Student in PISA 2018 performed one level below the average OECD student. Learning in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 towards society 5.0 in an educational perspective is carried out by integrating various aspects including literacy and numeracy that affect the achievement of national education goals, the Philippines education system need to adjust relevant learning

patterns because changes in students' assessment are noticed in recent years. To address the gap, the Philippine government has made various innovations, programs and policies in the educational system to improve the quality of education. One of the programs made is the implementation of the National Learning Camp 2023.

The Department of Education Philippines, proposed the National Learning Camp (NLC) to address learning loss and enhance teacher competence. The NLC is a voluntary program that is starting its phased implementation with Grade 7 & 8 learners focusing on English, Science, and Mathematics. The Department Order Number 014, s. 2023, states that the NLC is designed to provide additional teaching support to enhance learner's academic performance. The Department of Education believes that the NLC would help improve learning outcomes for all learners, regardless of their background or abilities. It will also provide teachers with the opportunity to learn from each other and develop their teaching skills through collaboration with others. The "Efficacy of National Learning Camp to Literacy and Numeracy of Grade 7 Learners" is a research problem of paramount importance, as it seeks to determine the effectiveness of National Learning Camp to the literacy and numeracy of Grade 7 learners as an essential educational intervention on the foundational skills of high school learners.

Literature Review:

Numeracy is defined as the ability to understand and use numbers. In addition to basic reading and writing skills, today's consumers need an understanding of numbers and basic mathematical skills use any numeral information presented in text, tables or charts. This is especially true in many financial and healthcare settings, where a basic understanding of numerical concept is arguably as important for informed decision making as reading ability (Dieckmann, et.al 2019)

According to Li, 2022, Academic Literacy as an embodiment of higher-order language and thinking skills within the academic community bears huge significance for language socialization, resource distribution and even power disposition within the larger sociocultural context.

Methodology:

Research Design

The quantitative research design using quasi-experimental approach was employed in this study to determine the effect of National Learning Camp to literacy and numeracy of Grade 7 learners. Likewise, the design was utilized to determine the significant differences between the pretest and posttest.

Subjects of the Study

The study subjects were 25 students of Grade 7 of Bug-ang National High School Officially Enrolled during the School Year 2022-2023 and now grade 8 learners in SY 2023-2024.

Sampling Technique

This study employed the purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling refers to a group of non-probability sampling techniques in which units are selected because they have the characteristics that we need in our sample. It is common in qualitative research and mixed methods research. The 25 Grade 7 learners of Bug-ang National High School Grade who participated in the National Learning Camp were the samples of the study.

Research Instrument

The researchers used two standardized instrument tools to determine the efficacy of the Grade 7 learners to Numeracy and Efficacy; The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) for literacy and the Enhanced Regional Unified Numeracy Test for the Numeracy. The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) is an assessment tool composed of graded passages designed to determine a student's reading level (Phil-IRI Resource Learning Package 2022-2023). It is conducted twice per school year. The first test was for Pre-test and the second test was for the post-test. Next, the Enhanced Regional Unified Numeracy Test was intended for all Grades 1 to Grade 11 learners in all public and private schools in DepEd Region VII. It measures the learners' competencies in the four fundamental operations in Mathematics (Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication, and Division) and Understanding numbers and problem-solving as well (RM. 827, 2022, DepEd Region VI, 2022). the E-RUNT will be conducted twice for pre-test and post-test. The Researchers utilized the pre-test and posttest data of e-runt to determine the efficacy of the learners to numeracy before and after the National Learning Camp.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

Since the research Instrument is based on the standard tool designed by the Department of Education, therefore, there is no validity or reliability of the instrument used.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the study, the researcher sought permission from the Office of the Schools District Supervisor of Toboso, Division of Negros Occidental, and the office of the Bug-ang National High School principal to conduct the research instrument on the target participants. After the approval letter, the researcher gathered the posttest data of the

Grade 7 learners SY 2022-2023 and the pretest data of Grade 8 SY 2023-2024. After acquiring the needed data, these were carefully tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted according to this study's specific problems and hypotheses.

Data Analysis Procedure

The various data gathered through the test materials were subjected to statistical treatment using the SPSS 17 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). To describe the reading performance of the respondents, the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Tool was used. The tool consists of a reading passage and seven (7) questions to test the reader's comprehension. The ratings and their interpretation below were used.

Mean Score (out of 7)	Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
5.60 – 7.00	80.00 – 100%	Independent
4.13 – 5.59	59.00 – 79.99%	Instructional
0.00 – 4.12	0.00 – 58.99%	Frustration

To describe the numeracy performance of the respondents, the Enhanced-Regional Unified Numeracy Test (E-RUNT) Tool was used. The tool is a forty-item test on numeracy with ten (10) items for each fundamental operation on integers (addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division). The ratings and their interpretation below were used.

Score	Verbal Interpretation
36 – 40	Highly Proficient
30 – 35	Proficient
20 – 29	Nearly Proficient
10 – 19	Low Proficient
0 – 9	Not Proficient

Ethical Consideration

In adherence to the ethical issues, the researcher observed important considerations and protocols: First, the researcher asked for consent from the office district supervisor and school office in-charge regarding to the conduct of the study. Second, the researcher ensured the confidentiality of the participants' real identities; their individual scores were protected and not revealed.

Findings and Discussion:

This part of the research report presents, analyzes, and interprets the gathered data concerning the specific problems and hypotheses outlined in this study.

Table 1
Reading Performance of the Respondents in the Pretest and Posttest

Variables	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Pretest	25	4.04	1.594	Frustration
Posttest	25	5.68	1.030	Independent

Table 1 shows the reading performance of Grade 7 students in the pretest and posttest. The pretest result showed a standard deviation of 1.594 and a mean of 4.04 interpreted as frustration level. The posttest result shows a standard deviation of 1.030 and a mean of 5.68 interpreted as an independent level.

Table 2
Numeracy Performance of the Respondents in the Pretest and Posttest

Variables	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Pretest	25	28.24	5.101	Nearly Proficient

performance of Grade 7 students in the pretest and posttest. Because the p-value of .000 is connected with the t-value being lower at the 0.05 level, it will reject the hypothesis in the learners' numeracy performance before and after participation in the National Learning Camp. The result of the posttest implies that the participation of the Grade 7 students in the National Learning Camp caused significant improvements in their numeracy performance. As a result of the findings, it can be concluded that learners' performance in both literacy and numeracy improved once they participated in the National Learning Camp. Moreover, this study implies that the NLC is proven of its efficacy towards the improvement of numeracy and literacy of learners thus; the performance of the learners would be improved if proper implementation of the policies and programs of DepEd like National Learning Camp is properly implemented and supported by the stakeholders such as parents and others, monitoring and evaluation of National Learning Camp should be strengthened by the school head and other implementors in the higher offices, and feedbacking on the result of National Learning within the school and district is a must. Furthermore, the dissemination of the National Learning Camp results to parents and teachers to advocate its efficacy and finally, National Learning Camp will be offered to all Grade Level considering its great impact and efficacy to learners' numeracy and literacy performance.

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